

Approach to a Project and its Risk Assessment

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Forewords

A good idea many times turns into a project intending to succeed and meet the purposed goals. When the project is born, its promoters must be conscious of unexpected difficulties. This writing is an alert for the complexity of a project, and its going on and after risks. We speak in general and not to specific areas to alert future entrepreneurs of the importance of having a straight discipline in the project and the pretended goals. A nuanced approach to Risk also complements the second phase after the project is terminated.

The Project

Project requirements

- Clear objectives
- Achievable results
- Definition of direct beneficiaries
- Spatial location
- Duration
- Definition of resources

Types of Projects

- Investment Projects
- Social projects
- Institutional Projects

Project live cycle

A project is developed in a life cycle constitutes a sequence of phases from the initial idea to its conclusion.

Project Management

They are procedures that organize and give complementarily to phases or processes.

Phases of a Project

Initiation phase:

- * This phase starts the project
- * It is a response to a perception of Initiation external demand or needs, or It is a response to an opportunity detected by project organization or project group
- * Better identifies the need/opportunity and the how-to supply it is the phase of the first assessment of resources and costs
- * Needs the organization's commitment to move on to the next stages

- Planning

- * Uses the information gathered in the initiation phase. Progressively establish the scope of the project.
- * Detailed planning (definition).
- * Product details. Establishes all activities and "work packages."
- * Defines the requirements, as well inputs and outputs needed.
- * Defines interfaces and technical procedures to be used Defines the control scheme

- Execution phase:

- Execution

It puts all planned tasks into execution. It is characterized by high teamwork. General coordination of the project manager. Decentralized management actions. Aim to achieve the objectives of:

- Deadlines
- Costs
- Quality
- * Continuous interaction with the control phase
- * General coordination of the project manager
- * Decentralized management actions
- * It aims to fulfill the objectives of Deadlines - Costs - Quality
- * Continuous interaction with the control phase

- Control phase:

The project control phase follows step by step and execution.

It gives touches and adjustments in planning.

Seeks to keep the scope of the project

It is diluted in the different specific managements, but it coordinates by the change control, a critical integration management process.

Verifies the fulfillment of the objectives of:

* Deadlines

* Costs

* Quality

- Closing phase:

* Goals achieved, product delivery done,

* Closing

* Accepting the product

- Dissolution of the team.

Essential components of a Project

- Project identification
- Importance and justification
- Project horizon
- Superior objective
- Immediate objective (s)
- Methodology
- Expected products(Goals)
- Description and schedule of activities
- Quantification and budgeting the activities
- Implementation strategy

- Technical team specification
- Required inputs (Q and \$)
- Counterparty offered

Main Goal

It is the main objective linked to programs of development to which the project proposes to contribute. It is associated with the project impact.

It is the objective that the project offers to achieve in its immediate goals. It must be concise and related to the principal purpose. In terms of the scope, results correspond to the project's effect, also called specific objective or desired situation to be sought at the end of the project horizon.

Concepts:

* Inputs. They are the necessary means for carrying out the activities from the project. From the details of the activities is that the inputs are specified and quantified from the project.

* Plan of implementation. Corresponds to the set of products, activities, and project inputs related to the strategy of action of the project (The variety of means to be mobilized to achieve the objectives, outcomes, and execution of project activities)

* Indicators. Qualitative or quantitative expressions are the indicative achievement of goals, products, and performance of project activities. They express quantity, quality, and time specify to obtain the desired information regarding the indicators quantity, quality, and time (location and cost when required).

* Assumption check indicators receive outside the project's control that may influence achieving its objectives and products and executing.

* Risk factors are factors exogenous to the project, whose occurrence promises the achievement of goals, outcomes, and activities. Not to be confused with the prerequisite.

Risk pre-requirements in the execution of project activities.

These are pre-conditions inherent to the project without which PRE organization responsible for implementation would not be able –

* Requirements the organization accountable for execution would not execute it, such as management capacity and personnel with the minimum necessary qualification.

* Follow up – Focuses on the project's implementation plan during its implementation phase, constituting an essential tool for project management.

* Evaluation: Its purpose is to assess the achievement of results, objectives, and project development objectives. It is related to the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness of the project.

* Effective - It is associated with the project's implementation plan. It is the appropriate choice of activities to reach the products and explain the effects that guarantee the reach.

* Effectiveness: It is the capacity for articulation and management that makes project objectives. It is related to the immediate goals of the project. It means doing what is to do. It Makes things happen in terms of the final benefits of the project. It encompasses the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness and is related to the project's development objectives.

The Risk

Concept

Risk is the quantification and qualification of uncertainty, both concerning losses and gains by individuals or organizations.

Being the Risk inherent in any activity - and impossible to eliminate -, its administration is a crucial element for the survival of institutions and companies.

The Risk is composed of internal and external risk factors - causes -. There is a need to explore Risk into its respective causes.

An underlying premise of risks is that every profitable or public organization exists to generate value for the interested parties. All organizations face uncertainty. The challenge for management is to determine the level of uncertainty prepared to cope it strives to increase value for stakeholders.

Uncertainties generate risks and opportunities, with the potential to destroy generate value. Corporate risk management enables administrators to effectively address uncertainties, risks, and opportunities associated with them to improve the capacity to generate value.

Companies worldwide are volatile, dynamic, and too conflicted, need to manage their risks. So they can do with effectiveness must have a structured process, with established methodology and criteria, must have a corporate risk management system.

A relevant aspect of the corporate risk management system that must be defined and implemented throughout the company is its Risk exposure.

What is Risk exposure?

Risk exposure is the amount of Risk that the company wants to take to achieve its goals. Or we can also say that Risk exposure is the number of risks, in the broader sense that an organization is willing to accept in their quest to add value. The Risk expose reflects the entire administrative philosophy of an organization and, in turn, influences its culture and operational style.

The quantification of Risk exposure allows determining the risk x benefit binomial, controlling and maintaining risks at levels desired.

It must be considered Risks x Opportunities x Exposure to Risk to serve as a guide for decision making, resource allocation, and definition alignment of the decision.

Many organizations consider this exposure qualitative, categorized as high, moderate, or low, while other organizations take a quantitative approach that reflects and balances the goals of growth, return and risk. An organization with a greater risk desire may wish to allocate a large portion of its capital to high-risk areas as new emerging markets.

On the other hand, an organization with a reduced risk appetite may limit its short-term Risk by investing only in markets mature and stable.

The risk desire is directly related to the organization's strategy and is taken into account when defining the process since these expose the organization to different risks.

Management of these helps management to select a strategy capable of aligning value creation with Risk expose.

Value is generated, conserved, or destroyed by management decisions. Value creation occurs by exploiting resources, such as personnel, capital, technology, and brand, the benefit obtained is greater than the resources used.

Value preservation occurs when the value generated is sustained through, among other things, the superior quality of the product, production capacity, and customer satisfaction.

The value may corrode if these goals are not achieved because of deficiencies in the strategy or its execution. The recognition of risks and opportunities, a factor inherent in the decision-making process, requires analyzing the information concerning the internal and external environments, using its resources, and adjusting the activities to the changing circumstances.

Value is maximized when management establishes strategy and objectives to achieve an ideal balance point between growth and growth targets return and the risks related to them and exploit resources efficiently and effectively to accomplish its goals.

The process of fixing Risk expose is specific to each company, considering that there is no value or value pre-fixed magic formula that determines the respective exposition.

The responsibility for this definition lies with the Company's Board of Directors, suggested by the Executive Board, through the President. He has to consider that the nature of risks, the business environment, the organization's internal environment, the business strategies, and objectives can and should be reviewed at all times, as they are in constant mutation.

Risk Tolerance and Capacity

In determining risk appetite, it's needed to have two other metrics: tolerance and capacity. So while desire is the level of Risk that the company wants to accept, it feels comfortable with, the one where managers can get and work with peace of mind.

Tolerance is the deviation from the risk exposure level. On the other hand, taking risks will be the maximum Risk that the organization can bear to pursue its goals. Thus, risk tolerance will serve as an alert to prevent the company from reaching the established level for its ability, jeopardizing its business continuity.

Risk tolerance represents the acceptable level of variation from the target for the fulfillment of a specific objective. As a rule, it is measured in the same units used to assess the aim of which it is linked.

When establishing risk tolerance, management considers the degree of importance of the related objects and aligns these tolerances to corporate Risk exposure. Such an operation helps to ensure that the organization remains within its limits of risk exposures and, in turn, achieves its goals.

The great importance of having metrics, qualitative and or quantitative aspects of exposing, tolerance, and risk capacity defined is that with these clear and objective definitions, the organization is protected from a general manager and or from a director who cancels controls and decides to risk it, in this case, whatever your intention,

This definition is of most importance, so that decision strategies are taken with awareness and serenity.

The critical point is that management considers the first Risk expose when evaluating strategic options and setting objectives compatible with the chosen strategy, and developing mechanisms to manage the implicit risks.

The uncertainty resulting from the amount of information available to support deliberations at the most diverse organizational levels has become increasingly present, reducing the ability to distinguish between several options in a broader context.

It is precisely the effect that this uncertainty has on an organization's objectives that is the Risk.

Thus, to obtain a decision based on technical knowledge, institutions must manage risks, identifying and analyzing them, accept their practical assessment, and support decision-making, be it in the sphere political, strategic, or operational.

In this sense, the Intelligence activity, defined as one that seeks to transform data into knowledge through its methodology, can significantly contribute to challenges encountered today.

Decision-makers who are motivated by the need to predict or control often face a complex system of components correlated, such as resources, desired results or objectives, people or groups of people; he is interested in analyzing that system. Presumably, the better he understands this complexity, the better is his decision.

Risk Analysis (AR) appears on this track. It provides its user knowledge organized and processed with a specific methodology, suggesting actions and measures to prevent or correct possible failures detected in a given process. Based on this analysis, it is possible to provide better decision-making assistance.

The risk management process m minimizes the occurrence of surprises and losses; improves incident prevention; improves controls; allows the most effective use of the material and human resources; improves operational effectiveness and efficiency; increases the organization's resilience; preserves the institution's assets.

Risk Management Cycle

The Risk Management cycle is translated through a structure of a continuous and sequential process, composed of five phases: Context Establishment, Risk Identification, Risk Estimation, Risk Assessment, and Risk Treatment.

1.1 Communication and Consultation

"Communication and Consultation" is a standard procedure in the Risk Management process. Initial plans are developed to inform the need and the decision taken to carry out the respective analysis.

These initial plans must be disseminated to all interested parties, whether internal or external, to explain the work to be carried out, emphasizing its importance and the

need to consult the specialists of the system, in addition to requesting opinions and existing data.

Based on these plans, the system's diagnosis will be allowing the preliminary identification of possible risks, their causes, their probable effects, and, when appropriate, some recognized measures to treat them.

Communication and Consultation make, through the dialogue, so that internal and external audiences understand the reasons for decisions and measures to be taken.

This cyclic and permanent procedure facilitates identifying different points of view and must be adequately considered, as they are essential sources of information.

1.2 Monitoring and Critical Analysis

As in Communication and Consultation, "Monitoring and Critical Analysis" is not a step, but a standard process procedure Risk Management. In this process, actions are developed to verify, supervise, observe, control, and review management's functioning.

It is, therefore, a necessary follow-up procedure, the objective of which is the continuous improvement of Risk Management by considering it an essential part of the PDCC Cycle (Plan, Do, Check, and Correct):

Thus, the "Monitoring and Critical Analysis" process must be planned as part of risk management, covering checking and regular checks. It can be periodic or happen in response to a specific fact.

Covering all phases and steps of the procedure, the Monitoring and Critical Analysis affects:

- Ensure the effectiveness of the control measures established;
- Obtain additional data and information for risk assessment;
- Analyze events and occurrences, their changes and trends, seeking to increase learning about them;

1.3 Setting the context

"Establishment Context" is the first stage of a process in which an initial diagnosis of the system to be analyzed.

The goal here is to provide support for the next step ("Risk Identification") through techniques capable of pointing out threats, which can be natural and human,

intentional or accidental, and the vulnerabilities that endanger the assets to be protected by the institution.

It's necessary for extensive and detailed mapping of the system's external and internal environments to be analyzed.

It must be well delimited and precisely demarcated.

The external context is the organization's relationship with the community, the country, legislation, economic and political structure, which may impact its institutional objectives. Understanding the external context is essential to ensure that all parties' goals and concerns are considered when developing risk criteria.

Therefore, for its elaboration, one must take into account, among others, the following aspects: geographical location, cultural, social, political, legal, regulatory, financial, technological, economic, natural, and competitive, whether international, national, regional, or local;

Key factors and trends that impact the organization's objectives and relationships with external stakeholders and their perceptions and values. This assessment may indicate possible threats to the institution's assets.

It is the environment in which the organization seeks to achieve its objectives in line with its mission, culture, processes, structure, and strategy.

An internal context is considered to be everything within the organization, influencing how risks are managed.

Among other elements, it is extracted from this analysis the vulnerabilities to which the organization is subject.

An organization's assets are essential elements in a risk assessment, and their recognition becomes necessary, as the Risk will always influence its integrity.

The process for identifying it can be simple, such as the use of Checklists, or more detailed, requiring an inventory of capital equipment, system traceability matrix, review of legal documents.

Thus, for the correct establishment of the context, the risks, when identifying assets, threats, and vulnerabilities, you must make an Assessment, whose knowledge is the result of reasoning prepared by the Intelligence professional and expresses the state of opinion concerning the truth about past and present fact or situation.

The analyst must keep in mind the purpose of knowledge and its respective delimitation to meet the report's objective: Risk Analysis.

At this stage, it is essential to survey the statistical background of each point and collect the opinions and needs of stakeholders and experts. When appropriate, predictions about potential consequences of a fact that can affect the assets to be protected are also recommended.

Conclusion

An entrepreneur, being already in the market or willing to grow or start a business or either an institution already with activities or ready to start movements, when they decide to draw a project for future implementation they have to take care of two critical factors:

1 – A project has a lifelike explained, and it is a complex of activities all related to the conception, beginning, and end.

2 – This continuum of the cycle of a project has a factor that depends on its success called "Risk."

3 – Both are intrinsically linked and must be watched side aside.

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